

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Leadership and goal achievement of the staff at Rancho Nápoles restaurant in Rocafuerte canton

Liderazgo y el cumplimiento de metas del personal del restaurante
Rancho Nápoles del cantón Rocafuerte

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Abstract This research was conducted to determine whether there is a relationship between leadership and goal achievement at Restaurante Rancho Nápoles in the Rocafuerte canton. The study followed a mixed-methods approach (quantitative and qualitative), with a non-experimental, descriptive, documentary, analytical, and cross-sectional design. Interviews and surveys were instruments, and data were processed using Excel. The results showed the presence of various leadership styles: authoritarian, democratic, charismatic, transformational, and *laissez-faire*. Each style affects motivation, group cohesion, and organizational performance differently. Authoritarian leadership limits participation, while democratic and transformational styles encourage collaboration and team development. Charismatic leadership is motivated by the leader's personality, and *laissez-faire* grants autonomy, which can lead to disorganization if not correctly managed. The study concludes a significant correlation between the leadership style applied and achieving goals, highlighting the importance of effective leadership management to improve organizational outcomes in this type of business.

Keywords leadership, goal achievement, leadership styles, work motivation, organizational performance.

Resumen Esta investigación se realizó para determinar si existe relación entre el liderazgo y el cumplimiento de metas en el Restaurante Rancho Nápoles del cantón Rocafuerte. El estudio fue de enfoque mixto (cuantitativo y cualitativo), con un diseño no experimental, de tipo descriptivo, documental, analítico y transversal. Se aplicaron entrevistas y encuestas como instrumentos, y los datos fueron procesados en Excel. Los resultados evidenciaron la presencia de varios estilos de liderazgo: autoritario, democrático, carismático, transformacional y *laissez-faire*. Cada uno influye de manera distinta en la motivación, cohesión del grupo y desempeño organizacional. El liderazgo autoritario tiende a limitar la participación, mientras que el democrático y el transformacional promueven la colaboración y el desarrollo del equipo. El liderazgo carismático motiva por la personalidad del líder, y el *laissez-faire* otorga autonomía, aunque puede generar desorganización si no se aplica con criterio. Se concluye que existe una correlación significativa entre el estilo de liderazgo aplicado y el cumplimiento de metas, lo que resalta la importancia de una gestión adecuada del liderazgo para mejorar los resultados organizacionales en este tipo de negocios.

Palabras clave liderazgo, cumplimiento de metas, estilos de liderazgo, motivación laboral y desempeño organizacional.

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Introduction

Companies must have a person who manifests ethical and moral values and a sense of collaboration for their company; this person is known as a leader, and these same people achieve the success of their organizations (Herrera et al., 2017). Leadership involves the use of the skills and characteristics of a leader to influence other people and meet the goals set (Geraldo et al., 2020). On the other hand, the fulfillment of goals, according to Rojas (2019), is based on the definition of a deadline or stage of completion of an activity; it tries to have achievable and tangible goals, which generates a significant challenge in the process of achieving said activity.

In other words, leadership is vital to the survival of any organization. It provides the direction, motivation, decision-making, and crisis management necessary to face the challenges of the business environment and achieve goals. This research paper is based on the fundamental need to analyze the importance of leadership and its influence on the staff of the Rancho Nápoles restaurant in Rocafuerte Canton in achieving goals.

Leadership is considered globally an essential and fundamental element because, as Alatrística (2020) indicates, employees are required to establish a solid relationship with the company and with their leader. This relationship must be based on trust and mutual respect, which will facilitate workers' commitment and effort (Alatrística, 2020). Trust and respect are the basis for building a relationship between employees and the company, which can foster a positive and productive work environment.

Peláez (2021) observes that leadership today demands more than just adherence to conventional organizational traits like specialization and productivity. In his study in Madrid, Spain, he highlights a shift toward embracing innovative approaches to development, governance, and cultivating new skills and competencies. These emerging strategies aim to enhance leaders' ability to support and empower their teams, ultimately contributing to employee growth, organizational well-being, and sustained competitiveness in a dynamic business environment.

In the current global scenario, companies are forced to pay attention to leadership. Romero et al. (2021) comment that, in Mexico, it is important for companies to implement effective leadership programs, as they need their employees to contribute to achieving organizational objectives. Leadership is also fostered through personal growth and can be cultivated in every organization member. In short, a focus on leadership and its personalized development emerges as a fundamental element for the progress and competitiveness

of companies in the current scenario.

Leadership and goal achievement are fundamental to a company's progress. Peláez (2021) indicates that when an organization's culture promotes achieving goals and objectives, it motivates employees to achieve results that exceed their expectations. On the other hand, Lugo (2016) indicates that leaders are an essential part of business development and are not limited to hierarchical positions. Being part of work groups can significantly change tasks, influencing people and the organization's overall results. Based on the above, this research aims to analyze the relationship between leadership and goal achievement at the Rancho Nápoles Restaurant in the Rocafuerte canton.

Methodology

The present study adopts a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative elements to examine the leadership practices at the Rancho Nápoles Restaurant. This methodology combines the strengths of each approach while mitigating their limitations (Delgado et al., 2018). Quantitative data will be obtained through Likert-scale surveys administered to all 40 employees, as the entire population is accessible and no sampling is required (Arias, 2012; Escalante, 2017). These data will undergo statistical processing and analysis, using tools such as Cronbach's alpha to ensure reliability.

Qualitative data will be collected through semi-structured interviews with employees at various hierarchical levels, aiming to understand the influence of leadership on goal achievement (Escalante, 2017). The study employs a non-experimental, cross-sectional design, observing variables in their natural setting without manipulation and collecting data at a single point (Radhakrishnan, 2013; Huarie, 2019).

Research techniques include interviews and surveys, with instruments such as questionnaires, audio recordings, and photographs to support data collection (Arias, 2012). The analysis will incorporate descriptive, documentary, analytical, and statistical methods to interpret both primary and secondary data, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the role of leadership in organizational performance (García & García, 2012; Burgos et al., 2021).

Results and discussion

Next, we will examine the results of the data collection techniques used in this study. First, we will examine the results of the surveys administered to Rancho Nápoles staff regarding leadership and achieving restaurant goals.

Within this context, the questions posed to Rancho Nápoles staff to better understand the leadership and goal-achievement variables will be presented. Twelve questions pertain to the former and 10 to the latter. Dimensions such as authoritarian, democratic, bureaucratic, charismatic, transformational, and laissez-faire leadership were assessed, as well as dimensions of David McClelland’s needs theory and two-factor theory.

Figure 1. Authoritarian leadership dimension.

Regarding the first question, the majority of respondents (60%) disagree that the leader imposes his ideas without considering the opinions of others, either because they disagree (30%) or strongly disagree (30%). This suggests that the leader considers the team’s opinions when making decisions. However, 15% strongly agree with the statement, indicating that the leader sometimes imposes his ideas without considering others.

In the second question, most respondents (90%) (20% + %70) agreed or strongly agreed that the leader maintains strict control over the team’s tasks and activities. This indicates that authoritarian leadership manifests itself primarily in a high level of control and supervision by the leader. Only 5% disagreed with this statement, suggesting that the leader does not delegate responsibilities or grant autonomy to the team.

In summary, the analysis of the two questions shows that authoritarian leadership is characterized more by strict control of activities than by imposing ideas without considering others. Although most people do not perceive the leader as completely ignoring the team’s opinions, there is a tendency toward a directive and controlling leadership style.

Regarding the first question, there is a positive consensus, as 76% of respondents (38% + 38%) feel optimistic about the team’s participation in decision-making. This suggests that most team members perceive that the leader promotes a participatory environment. On the other hand, 12% remain neutral, and another 12% disagree. This indicates that a small group may be dissatisfied with the level of participa-

Figure 2. Democratic leadership dimension.

In the second question of this dimension, 88% of respondents (63% + 35%) feel positive about the delegation of responsibilities. This is a strong indicator that the leader excellently empowers team members, which is fundamental to democratic leadership. As with the first question, 12% disagree with this question. This percentage is consistent with the first question, suggesting that there is a group that could benefit from greater clarity in responsibilities and empowerment. In summary, the results indicate that the leader has a mostly positive approach to participation and delegation, which is fundamental to effective democratic leadership. It is important to address the concerns of the 12% who feel neutral or disagree.

Figure 3. Bureaucratic leadership dimension.

In the first question of the bureaucratic leadership dimension, 63% of respondents (25% + 38%) favor the leader’s adherence to established policies and procedures, suggesting that most perceive leadership as following organizational guidelines. A further 25% of respondents remain neutral, which could indicate that some have no clear opinion or have observed mixed behaviors in the leader. Only 12% of respondents disagree, which is a relatively low percentage and could indicate that bureaucratic leadership is generally accepted in this dimension.

In short, the leader appears to be viewed as someone who adheres to policies and procedures, which can be positive in an environment that values structure and regulation. Howev-

er, the neutrality of a quarter of respondents suggests there is room for improvement in the perception of leadership in this regard.

In the second question, 86% of respondents (48% + 38%) agree that the leader emphasizes compliance with rules and regulations. This shows a strong alignment with the principles of bureaucratic leadership, which focuses on adherence to rules. Only 14% remain neutral, indicating that the majority has a strong opinion about the leader’s approach to rules.

Leadership in this dimension is highly valued. There is a strong emphasis on compliance with rules, which can contribute to a more organized and predictable work environment. The absence of negative responses reinforces the leader’s positive perception.

Figure 4. Charismatic leadership dimension.

In the first question on the charismatic leadership dimension, 38% of respondents strongly agreed, 42% agreed, 12% were neutral, and 8% disagreed. This indicates that most team members (80%) perceive that their leader inspires and motivates them with their vision and enthusiasm. However, 12% remained neutral and 8% disagreed, suggesting room for improvement.

In this second question, 65% of respondents strongly agreed, 13% agreed, and 22% were neutral. These results show that a large portion of the team (78%) believes their leader can generate a strong emotional bond with them. However, 22% remained neutral, indicating that there is still room to strengthen these emotional bonds.

In summary, the results suggest that the leader has a good level of charisma and the ability to inspire and motivate his team and generate emotional bonds. However, a few members do not perceive these aspects positively, so improving the connection with the entire team would be advisable.

In the first question on the transformational leadership dimension, 88% of respondents (28% + 60%) favor the leader’s ability to stimulate the team intellectually. This indicates that the majority perceives the leader as fostering an environment conducive to creativity and innovation. The 12% neutral responses suggest that a small group has no clear

opinion. This could indicate a need for deeper communication about innovation and creativity initiatives.

Figure 5. Transformational leadership dimension.

In the second question, 88% of respondents also expressed positive opinions regarding the leader’s ability to inspire the team. This is a positive indication that leadership is aligned with organizational goals.

In summary, the perception of transformational leadership is positive, with a high percentage of favorable responses to both questions. However, team members’ perceptions of intellectual stimulation and inspiration toward organizational goals could be improved.

Figure 6. Laissez Faire leadership dimension.

In the first question of the laissez-faire leadership dimension, the majority of respondents (47%) (45% + 2%) do not believe that the leader intellectually stimulates the team and fosters creativity and innovation, as they responded “disagree” or “strongly disagree.” This suggests that the leader could improve in this area.

In the second question, the majority (50%) of respondents (45% + 5%) believe that the leader is unable to inspire the team to go beyond their interests for the sake of organizational goals, as they responded “disagree” or “strongly disagree”. This indicates that the leader needs to improve his or her ability to inspire and motivate the team to achieve organizational goals. The results suggest that the leader has

room for improvement in intellectually stimulating the team and inspiring them to achieve organizational goals. Working on these aspects could strengthen his or her laissez-faire leadership style.

Figure 7. Dimension theory of need: David McClelland.

The first question in David McClelland’s need theories dimension shows a high need for achievement among respondents, as the majority feel satisfied when achieving goals, which indicates motivation for success and personal improvement. The high proportion of “strongly agree” (68%) and “agree” (22%) responses suggests that most respondents feel intense satisfaction when achieving goals in their work. This indicates a predominance of the need for achievement, which, according to McClelland, is characterized by the search for challenges and the desire to be recognized for achievements.

In the second question, 55% of respondents strongly agree that their job allows them to develop their full potential, while 20% disagree. This suggests that the majority (75%) feel their job provides them with opportunities to reach their full potential. However, the 25% who responded “neutral” may be an area for improvement for the organization, as it is important that all employees feel they have opportunities for growth and development in their jobs.

In the third question, 100% of respondents (75% strongly agreed + 25% agreed) identified with pride in overcoming challenges. This indicates that the majority of employees in the workplace value achievement and personal improvement. This feeling of pride is an indicator that individuals value success. This phenomenon reflects individuals’ intrinsic motivation and positively impacts job performance and organizational culture. The table reveals that the need for achievement is a significant motivation for employees in the workplace.

In the fourth question, 95% of respondents (70% strongly agreed + 25% agreed) feel that their job provides them with significant independence and control. This suggests a positive work environment that fosters autonomy, a key factor

for motivation and job satisfaction. Furthermore, it should be noted that only 5% of respondents were neutral, indicating that almost all employees have a clear opinion about their level of control at work. This could reflect an organizational culture that prioritizes autonomy.

In the fifth question, 72% of “strongly agree” responses indicate a strong sense of confidence and motivation among respondents to assume responsibilities. This suggests that most participants feel empowered and willing to face challenges, a positive indicator of a work or educational environment fostering personal and professional growth. Only 8% of neutral responses suggest little ambivalence regarding the ability to assume responsibilities. This may indicate that respondents perceive their abilities and do not feel indecisive about their ability to face challenges. In summary, the results of this question reflect a strong sense of self-efficacy and motivation among respondents to assume responsibilities and face challenges. Leveraging this tendency can be key to developing an environment that fosters individual growth and contributes to the organization’s success.

Figure 8. Dimension two-factor theory.

In the first question of the two-factor theory dimension, most respondents (86%) (63% + 23%) feel their work is valued and recognized, a positive indicator of intrinsic motivation. However, the 14% who remain neutral could see an opportunity to improve communication and recognition in the workplace. Superiors must implement strategies to increase the perception of recognition; it can directly influence job satisfaction and talent retention.

In the second question, 93% (26% + 68%) of respondents feel positive about the feedback they receive, suggesting a relatively effective performance appraisal system. However, the low percentage of those who remain neutral (7%) could indicate room for improvement in the quality or frequency of feedback. Regular feedback sessions could help increase employees’ perception of support and professional development.

In the third question, 88% (33% + 55%) of respondents believe a positive working environment and collaboration are

encouraging signs of a positive work environment. However, 12% of respondents declared themselves neutral, which may cause concern. This may indicate that some employees do not feel fully integrated or have a less positive work experience. Neutrality can signify disinterest or a lack of connection with the team. In short, although most employees perceive a positive work environment, it is important not to ignore those who feel neutral. Implementing strategies to improve integration and collaboration can lead to an even healthier and more productive work environment.

In the fourth question, a remarkable 100% of respondents feel they can count on the support of their colleagues and superiors, which is essential for a healthy and productive work environment. This high level of support can contribute to team resilience and improved performance. However, it is important to continue fostering an environment where everyone feels comfortable requesting and offering support.

In the fifth question, 100% of respondents considered interpersonal relationships at work to be positive and constructive. This is an exceptional result that suggests a harmonious work environment. However, it is crucial to maintain and strengthen these relationships through personal and professional development activities and fostering open communication.

Part of the results is analyzing the relationship between the two variables, considering that the data was collected through surveys.

Evaluation is a statistical measure that shows the relationship and strength of the link between two variables. It is expressed by the Pearson correlation coefficient, which ranges from -1 to 1. Its interpretation is as follows:

$a=1$: Perfect positive correlation; as one variable increases, the other also increases in the same proportion.

$a > 0$ and $a < 1$: Positive correlation; as one variable increases, the other also tends to increase.

$a=0$: There is no compensation or linear relationship between the variables.

$a < 0$ and $a > -1$: Negative correlation; As one variable increases, the other tends to decrease.

$a=-1$: Perfect negative correlation; as one variable increases, the other decreases in the same proportion.

In the context of the research on the Rancho Nápoles Restaurant, the evaluation of the variables “leadership” and “goal achievement” would allow us to analyze whether leadership style and quality are associated with the level of goal achievement by staff.

After applying the formula, the score is 0.65. This value indicates a moderately positive relationship between leadership and goal achievement. As the perception of good leader-

ship increases (for example, a democratic or transformational leadership style), goal achievement also tends to improve.

Although not a perfect relationship, this result suggests that leadership significantly impacts how restaurant employees achieve their goals. Leaders who foster motivation, open communication, and recognition create an environment where employees feel more motivated and work better toward achieving established goals.

Conclusions

At Rancho Nápoles Restaurant, various leadership styles—authoritarian, democratic, charismatic, transformational, and laissez-faire—shape team dynamics and influence goal achievement. The organizational culture emphasizes personal growth and goal attainment, with most employees showing strong commitment and motivation. A positive correlation exists between participative leadership and enhanced performance, while authoritarian or hands-off styles may hinder creativity and initiative. Team support and collaboration are also vital to overall success. To strengthen leadership and goal achievement, the restaurant has proposed measures such as fostering team participation, implementing recognition systems, offering professional development, clarifying roles, and promoting social activities to enhance cohesion.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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Data availability statement

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Statement on the use of AI

The authors acknowledge the use of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies to improve the readability and clarity of the article.

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